

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART III.

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The 4-methyl derivatives of bis-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo and benzyldene-2-thionaphthene and a few of its substituted products have been prepared. The dyeing shades on cotton and wool obtained from these substances when compared with those from the isomeric 5- and 6-methyl derivatives show that the 4-methyl dyes are lighter in colour than those of the 5-methyl derivatives but deeper than those of the 6-methyl compounds. Quantitative measurement of some of the dyes of the three series confirmed the result. It has also been found that the influence of the methyl group substituted in 4, 5 and 6 positions of the thionaphthene nucleus of the parent compounds is similar to that observed in the acenaphthenequinone series.

The 4- and 6-methyl derivatives of 2-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthryleneindigo have been prepared and their properties studied.

In previous parts of this series (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 659; 1937, **15**, 709) it was found that 5-methyl derivatives of bis-

FIG. 1.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to bis-2-thionaphthene-, bis-2(4-methyl)-, bis-2(5-methyl)- and bis-2(6-methyl)-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos.

2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo and of benzylidene-2-thionaphthene and a few of its substituted products (Friedlauder and Risse, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1924; Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 543) are deeper in colour than those of the corresponding 6-methyl compounds.

Again in the acenaphthenequinone series (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423; 1933, 10, 679; 1936, 13, 94; 1938, 15, 20) the influence of one methyl group upon the colour of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigo and its various derivatives, when the methyl substitution occurs in 4, 5 or 6 position of the thionaphthene nucleus, was qualitatively and quantitatively studied. It was observed that the influence of CH_3 substitution in 4 and also in 6 position of the thionaphthene nucleus is to lighten the colour and in 5 position is to deepen the colour of the parent compound.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of CH_3 group in 4-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of bis-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo and of benzylidene-2-thionaphthene and its derivatives (*loc. cit.*) with a view to examine if the result is similar to what was observed in the acenaphthenequinone series (Guha, *loc. cit.*). This led the author to condense 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (*Chem. Zentr.*, 928, 99, I, 759; E. P. 79489; U. S. P. 28037; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 23) with glyoxal, benzaldehyde, *p*-nitro-, and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde.

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to benzylidene-2(4-methyl)-, -2(5-methyl)- and -2(6-methyl)-thionaphthene.

Here also those aldehydes only were used which gave rise to compounds of fairly prominent colours in the 5- and 6-methyl series.

These 4-methyl-derivatives resemble in general the isomeric 5- and 6-methyl compounds in their solubility and in developing shades on cotton and on wool. They also dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid giving characteristic colours which resemble those developed from the corresponding 5-methyl compounds on similar treatment except the benzylidene-2-(4-methyl)-thionaphthene which develops a deeper colour than those of the corresponding 5- and 6-methyl compounds (Table I). The melting points go on decreasing with the CH_3 groups changing their positions from 4 to 5 and then to 6 position of the thionaphthene nucleus, except benzylidene-2-(methyl)-thionaphthenes where the m. p. rises in the 5-methyl compound and falls down in the 6-methyl derivative. This observation is interesting and quite contrary to that found in the acenaphthenequinone series (*loc. cit.*).

The dyeing shades on wool and on cotton obtained from these 4-methyl derivatives have been found to be deeper than those from the isomeric 6-methyl variety but lighter than those from the corresponding 5-methyl-compounds. Again a comparison of the colours of the dyeings on wool and on cotton of bis-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo and of benzylidene-2-thionaphthene and their 4-, 5-, and 6-methyl derivatives on wool indicates that the influence of CH_3 substitution in 4 and 6 position of the thionaphthene nucleus is to lighten the colour and the CH_3 substitution in 5 position deepens the colour. This result is exactly analogous to what was found in the acenaphthenequinone series.

The absorption spectra of some of the compounds of this series have been studied in xylene solution and the absorption curves (Figs. 1 and 2) have been drawn in the same way as mentioned in the acenaphthenequinone series (*loc. cit.*). A study of the curves and the absorption maxima confirmed the earlier qualitative deductions. In the case of the curves in Fig. 2, the position of the change in slope corresponding to the indication of absorption could not be very definitely done as will appear from the trace but the positions were tentatively fixed at the points marked with arrow head.

The absorption maximum of bis-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo has been obtained for its various methyl derivatives (Fig. 1).

The thionaphthene-1'-aceanthryleneindigos form with alkaline hydro-sulphite a light yellow vat from which light red ochre colour develops on cotton but full shades are not obtained in either of the two.

TABLE I.

M = Methyl. T = Thionaphthene. B = Benzylidene.

Names.	M. p.	Dyeing shades			Absorption maximum.
		Colour in conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	on wool.	on cotton.	
Bis-2-T-ethyleneindigo (<i>cf</i> Friedlander and Riise, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	303°(d).	Green	Dark red	Dark red	4835A*
Bis-2-(4-M)-T-ethyleneindigo	Above 312°	Deep green	Deep red	Violet red	4810
Bis-2-(5-M)-T-ethyleneindigo	307°(d).	"	Dark red	"	4920
Bis-2-(6-M)-T-ethyleneindigo	300°(d).	Green	Scarlet red	Deep scarlet red	4765
B-2(4-M)-T	132°	Violet red	Yellow	..	4400
B-2(5-M)-T	147°	Brownish red	"	...	4445
B-2(6-M)-T	134-35°	"	"	...	4320
4'-Nitro-B-2(4-M)-T	273°	Greenish blue	Deep yellow	Light orange	...
4'-Nitro-B-2(5-M)-T	264°	"	Orange yellow	Do.	...
4'-Nitro-B-2(6-M)-T	228-29°	Purple	Deep yellow	Yellowish orange	...
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2(4-M)-T	202°	Blue	Cinnabar red	Pink	...
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2(5-M)-T	198-99°	"	"	"	...
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2(6-M)-T	193°	Violet red	"	Light pink	...

EXPERIMENTAL.

The 4-methyl-indigoid dyes described here were prepared in the same way as the isomeric 5- and 6-methyl derivatives recorded in Parts I and II of this series.

bis-2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo.

It separated in fine deep red needles from the reaction mixture consisting of glyoxal sodium bisulphite (0.568 g.) in 15 c.c. of water and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (35 c.c.) and concen-

trated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). It was crystallised from toluene, m.p. above 312° . It is difficultly soluble in chloroform, amyl alcohol and moderately soluble in glacial acetic acid. It dyes wool in deep red shades from an acid bath and cotton in violet red shades from a deep yellow hydrosulphite vat. (Found : S, 18.51. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S, 18.28 per cent).

Benzylidene-2-(4-methyl)-thionaphthene.

It was prepared from benzaldehyde (0.424 g.), 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (11 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (2.5 c.c.), and crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine yellow rectangular crystals, m.p. 132° . It is soluble in petroleum ether. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is violet-red. It dyes wool in yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: S, 13.06. $C_{16}H_{12}OS$ requires S, 12.69 per cent).

4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-methyl)-thionaphthene was obtained as yellow-orange small needles from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.453 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 20 c.c. of hot absolute alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 273° . It is difficultly soluble in benzene and toluene. It dyes wool in deep yellow shades from an acid bath and cotton in light orange shades from a light brown hydrosulphite vat. (Found: S, 10.94. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3NS$ requires S, 10.77 per cent).

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(4-methyl)-thionaphthene separated as its hydrochloride in shining greenish yellow rectangular precipitate from *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.566 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.624 g.) in 13 c.c. of hot absolute alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1.6 c.c.). It gave on washing with dilute alcohol a bright vermilion dye (0.9372 g.). It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in diamond shaped shining crystals, m.p. 202° . It is difficultly soluble in petroleum ether. It dyes wool in cinnabar-red shade from an acid bath and cotton in pink colour from a faintly red vat. (Found: S, 10.65. $C_{18}H_{17}ONS$ requires S, 10.84 per cent).

bis-2-Thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo was obtained by heating on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours a mixture of glyoxal sodium bisulphite (1.136 g.) in

30 c.c. of water and 3-hydroxythionaphthene (1.4 g.) in 50 c.c. of hot absolute alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.). The silky dark-red crystalline precipitate (0.731 g.) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in rectangular plates, m.p. 303° (decomp.). It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour and dyes wool in dark-red shades from an acid bath and cotton in the same shade from a deep-yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat (*cf.* Friedlander and Risse, *loc. cit.*). (Found : S, 19.63. $C_{18}H_{10}O_2S_2$ requires S, 19.87 per cent).

2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthryleneindigo.

It separated as dark-brown microscopic needles from the reaction mixture consisting of aceanthraquinone (0.696 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.), 120 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, and was crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 305°. It is sparingly soluble in acetone, carbon tetrachloride, moderately soluble in amyl alcohol. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour and dyes wool in dark-brown shades from an acid bath. (Found : S, 8.12. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 8.46 per cent).

2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthryleneindigo was similarly prepared from aceanthraquinone (0.588 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.416 g.) in 85 c.c. of acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid as red-brown microscopic needles and crystallised from xylene. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is yellowish-green. It dyes wool in red-brown shades from an acid bath. It resembles in properties the above compound. (Found : S, 8.41. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 8.46 per cent).

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